

A Hospital-Based Study to Evaluate Sonographic Features of Invasive Ductal Breast Carcinomas for Prediction of Malignancy Grade: An Observational Study

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Abstract

Aim: The aim of the present study was to evaluate sonographic features of invasive ductal breast carcinomas for prediction of malignancy grade.

Material & methods: The present study was conducted in Department of Radiodiagnosis including 200 solid breast masses which were evaluated by ultrasound for the duration of 2 years.

Results: Most common age group was 51-60 years (55%), followed by 60 and more years age group (22%) and 41-50 years age group (20%). Painless mass in breast (75%), Ulceration (16%), Painful mass (24%) were common complaints seen in our study. We noted that 48% patients had duration of symptoms from 6 months to 1 year, while 22% patients had duration of symptoms less than 6 months. Irregular borders, horizontal orientation, circumscribed/lobulated/ microlobulated, hypoechoic patterns, hypovascular, abrupt interfaces, posterior acoustic shadow, microcalcifications, architectural distortion and lymphadenopathy were common findings in all grades of invasive duct carcinoma patients.

Conclusion: Malignancy grade of invasive ductal carcinoma can be predicted by heterogeneous echotexture of mass, abrupt interfaces, calcifications, posterior acoustic enhancement and/or presence of reversal/lack of diastolic flow margins.

Keywords: Breast Ultrasound, Invasive Ductal Carcinoma, Malignancy Grade.

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Introduction

Breast cancer become the most common female cancer in urban India with an annual incidence of approximately 1,44,000 new cases per year. [1] Approximately 80% of breast carcinomas are mainly invasive ductal carcinoma, followed by 10-15% of cases with invasive lobular carcinomas. [2] Ductal carcinoma in situ (DCIS) is defined as a malignant proliferation of epithelial cells confined to endothelial lobular units without invading the basement membrane. [3]

The most common finding of DCIS is the presence of microcalcifications in the mammography screening of asymptomatic patients. [4,5] Invasive duct carcinoma has a high mortality rate due to localized invasion, lymph node spread, and distant metastasis. Prognosis is usually poor with invasive type carcinoma. [6]

An early and accurate recognition of breast tumor with poor prognosis will, therefore, be beneficial for preoperative planning and outcome

improvement. Ultrasound is a safe, non-invasive and radiation free adjunct to mammography for the evaluation of palpable breast masses. The use of breast ultrasound has shown remarkable promise in distinguishing benign from malignant solid lesions. [7] It is also used as a primary screening tool for breast cancer in women who are pregnant, young women with high risk for breast cancer and who have increased breast density on mammogram. [8]

Ultrasound is used as a first line modality of imaging for breast masses in patients less than 35 years and as an adjunct to mammography in older patients. [9-12] Breast ultrasonography is considered to be an adjunct to screening mammography, although breast ultrasonography is superior to mammography in detecting lesions in patients with symptomatic DCIS. [13] The most common ultrasonographic findings of DCIS are a hypoechoic mass with an irregular shape and indistinct margin. [14,15] Additional findings include microcalcifications, ductal changes, or

structural distortions. [14-21] Therefore, knowledge of the sonographic appearances of breast cancers and their possible variations determined by the tumor biology is important for the ultrasound radiologist to minimize misdiagnosis.

Hence, present study was aimed to evaluate sonographic features of invasive ductal breast carcinomas for prediction of malignancy grade.

Material & Methods

The present study was conducted in Department of Radiodiagnosis, Indira Gandhi Institute of medical sciences (IGIMS), Patna, Bihar, India including 200 solid breast masses which were evaluated by ultrasound for the duration of 2 years.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients who were positive for invasive ductal carcinoma (IDC) of breast on core needle biopsy and had both sonographic images and histopathological data available.
- Age of the patients ranged from 31 years to 78 years.

Methodology

Ultrasound examination of breast masses was done on a Philips ultrasound machine unit (HD7/Clearvue 650) using linear, high frequency (3–12 MHz), and curvilinear (2–5 MHz) transducers. Each breast mass was assessed by two radiologists with experience of 10 or more years. Each mass was characterized on sonography based on its shape, orientation, margin, echo pattern, posterior features, calcifications, presence of associated features if any, and color flow. Biopsy specimens were examined and histopathological grading was done by senior pathologists.

Statistical Analysis

The results for qualitative data were presented in frequency and percentage. Chi-square test was used to find association between histological grades of IDC (dependent parameter) and their sonographic features (independent parameters). Ordinal regression was used to predict the contribution of each independent parameter to arrive at the final histological grade, which happens to be the dependent parameter in our study. The statistical analysis was done using SPSS 21.0 in this study. The significance level was used at $P \leq 0.05$.

Results

Table 1: Distribution of malignant breast tumors according to age

Age in years	N	%
0 – 40	6	3
41 – 50	40	20
51 – 60	110	55
>60	44	22

Most common age group was 51-60 years (55%), followed by 60 and more years age group (22%) and 41-50 years age group (20%).

Table 2: Symptoms and Duration of symptoms

Symptoms	N	%
Painless mass in breast	150	75
Ulceration	32	16
Painful mass	48	24
Nipple retraction	20	10
Nipple discharge	10	5
Duration of symptoms		
<6 months	44	22
6 months – 1 year	96	48
1year – 1.5years	34	17
1.5 years – 2 years	26	13

Painless mass in breast (75%), Ulceration (16%), Painful mass (24%) were common complaints seen in our study. We noted that 48% patients had duration of symptoms from 6 months to 1 year, while 22% patients had duration of symptoms less than 6 months.

Table 3:

Ultrasound findings	Histological grade			Total
	N=100	N=50	N=50	
Irregular	80	35	45	160 (80%)
Round	10	5	3	18 (9%)
Oval	10	10	2	22 (11%)
Orientation				
Horizontal	70	30	20	120 (60%)

Indifferent	20	8	22	50 (25%)
Not determinable	8	6	6	20 (10%)
Vertical	2	6	2	10 (5%)
Echo pattern				
Hypoechoic	52	38	30	114 (58%)
Complex	24	9	9	42 (21%)
Anechoic	14	4	6	24 (12%)
Isoechoic	4	3	3	10 (5%)
Hyperechoic	6	1	1	8 (4%)
Margin				
Circumscribed/lobulated/ Microlobulated	88	36	48	172 (86%)
Spiculated/angular	16	14	2	28 (14%)
Boundaries				
Abrupt interface	80	40	40	160 (80%)
Echogenic halo	20	10	10	40 (20%)
Vascularity				
Hypovascular	70	18	32	120 (60%)
Spotty	14	30	6	50 (25%)
Hypervascular	11	1	8	20 (10%)
Absent	5	1	4	10 (5%)
Posterior acoustic features				
Shadowing	46	20	14	80 (40%)
Enhancement	6	8	18	32 (16%)
Combined pattern	5	5	2	12 (6%)
Unchanged	43	17	16	76 (38%)
Others				
Microcalcification	35	22	33	90 (45%)
Architectural distortion	32	28	20	80(40%)
Changes in Cooper's ligaments	5	35	30	70(35%)
Lymphadenopathy	35	15	40	90(45%)

Irregular borders, horizontal orientation, circumscribed/lobulated/ microlobulated, hypoechoic patterns, hypovascular, abrupt interfaces, posterior acoustic shadow, microcalcification, architectural distortion and lymphadenopathy were common findings in all grades of invasive duct carcinoma patients.

Discussion

Majority of the breast carcinomas are usually asymptomatic and the usual mode of presentation is an incidental palpable lump or pain and rarely, they present with nipple discharge and skin changes. [22] With the development of various adjuvant treatment methods including chemotherapy, endocrine therapy, and radiation therapy, the treatment outcome for patients with breast cancer has improved. Ultrasound is used in many ways, not only as an initial diagnostic tool for confirmation of pathology determined from biopsies of the breast but also staging of breast cancer. It is also combined with mammography, a procedure called sonomammography to aid in better detection of breast cancer. [23,24]

Most common age group was 51-60 years (55%), followed by 60 and more years age group (22%) and 41-50 years age group (20%). Painless mass in

breast (75%), Ulceration (16%), Painful mass (24%) were common complaints seen in our study. While Kini et al [25] demonstrated that calcifications on preoperative mammography appeared to be associated with an increased risk of local recurrence and that fine linear branching microcalcification observed on mammography was associated with a poor survival rate. In spiculated margins strands of tissues are seen radiating out from an ill marginated mass producing a stellate appearance. Spiculations represent retraction of tissue strands towards the tumor due to fibrosis - as a result of desmoplastic reaction. Posterior acoustic properties of a mass are based on multiple factors like cellular components, stromal reaction and number of histological interfaces between fibrous and cellular components. [26]

We noted that 48% patients had duration of symptoms from 6 months to 1 year, while 22% patients had duration of symptoms less than 6 months. Irregular borders, horizontal orientation, circumscribed/lobulated/ microlobulated, hypoechoic patterns, hypovascular, abrupt interfaces, posterior acoustic shadow, microcalcification, architectural distortion and lymphadenopathy were common findings in all grades of invasive duct carcinoma patients. In a

similar Indian study authors noted that masses with complex solid cystic mass with heterogeneous echotexture, abrupt interfaces, calcifications and/or presence of reversal/lack of diastolic flow may suggest high grade of tumors. The finding of reversal/lack of diastolic flow in a breast mass was the strongest predictor of high grade of tumor in our study and warrants early lymph nodal sampling. Similar findings were noted in present study. Lamb et al [27] investigated the relationship between imaging characteristics and histologic grade. Strain elastography (SE) and shear-wave elastography (SWE) are the two most frequently used ultrasound elastography techniques in the breast. In Strain elastography (SE), stress is applied by repeated manual compression of the transducer, which provides a measurement of the deformed lesion relative to the surrounding normal tissue with a color display. [28] The other technique, shear-wave elastography (SWE), uses an acoustic radiation force impulse created by an ultrasound beam, which allows for the measurement of the propagation speed of shear waves within the tissue and quantifies the stiffness in either kilopascals or meters per second. [29]

Conclusion

Malignancy grade of invasive ductal carcinoma can be predicted by heterogeneous echotexture of mass, abrupt interfaces, calcifications, posterior acoustic enhancement and/or presence of reversal/lack of diastolic flow margins.

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